

DAMAGE TOLERANCE OF COMPOSITE AIRCRAFT STRUCTURES: ANALYSIS AND CERTIFICATION

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SUMMARY: The capability of current analytical methods based on stress and/or fracture mechanics principles, is reviewed with the objective of establishing whether the technology is sufficiently mature to be able to satisfy damage tolerance requirements of composite aircraft structure by analysis with some testing. In other words is it possible to establish initial delamination requirements in critical areas of the structure and then by analysis show that the structure is fail-safe - analogous to the assumed initial crack size in metals. Examples of usage of analytical methods in the design process are identified. Perceived barriers to the widespread use of these analysis methods in design and certification are also discussed. These include computational complexity, lack of standards for determination of material fracture properties, large amount of testing to obtain needed material constants and properties, and lack of independent verification test data.

KEYWORDS: damage tolerance, delamination initiation, impact damage modeling, crack tip element, fracture mechanics material properties, delamination buckling

INTRODUCTION

Damage tolerance of civil aircraft composite parts is addressed by requiring ultimate load strength capability in the presence of barely visible damage (BVID), limit load capability with visible damage, and a specified load below limit load with discrete source damage (DSD). This is illustrated in Fig. 1 by a plot of the required residual strength capability versus damage size. Three distinct damage zones are shown, each defined by specific regulation: Federal Aviation Regulation (FAR) 25.305 for ultimate load in the presence of BVID, FAR 25.571(b) for allowable damage limit, and FAR 25.571(e) for DSD. The two larger damages must be repaired and the structure restored to ultimate load capability at the next scheduled maintenance activity or in the case of DSD at the next airport stop. The admissible damage sizes that set ultimate, limit, and ferry flight loads are tied to damage detectability, see Fig 1. Thus the structure must be capable of sustaining ultimate load with undetectable damage, limit load with detectable damage, and ferry flight load with immediately obvious damage (to the pilot). The damage size at limit load is set at the boundary between detectable and readily detectable damage size, with the expectation that the aircraft will not be flying understrength for a long period of time.

The certification requirements outlined above are usually complied with by test. Elements, components, or full-scale structure containing damage induced by impact or Teflon inserts are tested to demonstrate ultimate or limit load capability for static and after fatigue loading. Usually no analysis is performed to show that the residual strength is adequate and that the

damage or delamination will not grow in service. As new analytical methods of strength and life predictions of damaged composite structure are being developed there is a need to integrate this technology into the certification process. Likewise, the developing American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) methods for characterization of fracture properties being established concurrently must be integrated with analysis and certification requirements.

Fig. 1: Allowable damage sizes

In this paper, the capability of current analytical methods, some developed under Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) sponsorship, and the test methods for material property determination are reviewed with the objective of establishing whether the technology is sufficiently mature to be able to satisfy damage tolerance requirements by analysis with some testing. In other words is it possible to establish initial delamination requirements in critical areas of of the structure and then by analysis show that the structure is fail safe - analogous to the assumed initial crack size in metals. Examples of usage of analytical methods in the actual design or repair process are also identified.

ANALYTICAL MODELING

For the analytical methods to have wide application they must be capable of computing stresses, strains, and strain-energy-release rates for a variety of problems common in composite airframe construction. Figure 2 identifies some locations where delaminations can be deleterious to structural integrity. These are either locations where high interlaminar stresses exist and delaminations can form (free edges, bonded joints, ply drop-offs, curved parts) or in the case of compression or shear loading pre-existing delaminations have a propensity to grow. In addition to modeling delaminations at diverse locations, the analysis should be capable of treating impact damage.

Detailed Finite Element Analysis (FEA) is capable of obtaining solutions to the problems posed in Fig. 2, but, because of many locations to be analyzed this quickly becomes impractical. FEA, however, is a useful tool to treat specialized problems and is used extensively as a check solution. To reduce the analysis complexity other methods have been developed to solve some of the cases shown in Fig. 2. These methods are based on (1) stress

analysis where computed stresses are compared to interlaminar material strengths, (2) stress analysis with empirical reduction of properties in the damage area, (3) sublaminar delamination buckling followed by fracture mechanics considerations, and (4) rigorous fracture mechanics with fracture mode decomposition.

Fig. 2: Critical locations of delaminations

Although stress analyses by themselves are not capable to model structural details containing a delamination, they are useful in locating high interlaminar stress areas before proceeding to a fracture mechanics analysis. Thus the availability of specialized program that can provide a quick assessment where the critical delaminations should be considered for a damage tolerance analysis is almost a pre-requisite. This will reduce the number of critical locations to manageable numbers. In Ref. 1, the following interlaminar or out-of-plane problems are addressed: (1) induced stresses in laminate corner radii, (2) induced stresses due to ply drop-off, (3) induced stresses due to panel buckling, (4) direct stresses due to fuel pressure loads, and (5) induced stresses due to stiffener runouts. The last problem was also addressed in [2]. In [1], an analysis method has been developed for each problem above together with companion software, and as these methods have been developed under FAA and U.S. Navy sponsorship they are available to the industry, at least in the United States. Free edge problem, see Fig. 2, is not addressed in [1], but there are many solutions available in the literature, [3] and [4] being representative.

Analytical prediction of the residual strength of a composite structure damaged by impact can be separated into two types of analysis. The first type should have the ability to characterize damage knowing impact parameters such as velocity, mass, shape of impactor, and the stiffness properties of the structure in question including support conditions. The second type of analysis would use the damage information from the first analysis to compute residual strength or damage growth. As at this time there is no widely accepted method to characterize damage analytically, the recourse has been to use stiffness reduction techniques to model the damage with the amount of reduction based on correlation with test data. In one such semi-empirical model [5], the degree of stiffness reduction is assumed to depend on the impact energy and the material system. The parameters considered are laminate lay-up, laminate thickness, material toughness, support conditions, and impactor size and geometry. Although this model is available to the industry there is a general lack of acceptance primarily due to the large amount of test data required to establish empirical constants. For example, description of the impact parameter requires five constants.

Solutions to the delamination buckling problem illustrated in Fig. 2 were developed in [6,7] under FAA and Navy sponsorship. Both are closed form solutions based on energy methods

but use different functions to model the displacement of the buckled portion of the laminate. Both solutions assume the unbuckled region does not displace and hence the formulation breaks down for thin laminates or for midplane delaminations. The solution first determines the buckling load for the thinner sublaminates and then proceeds to grow the delamination according to whether the critical total strain energy release rate has been exceeded. Failure is defined as initiation of delamination growth. The problem that is solved is an embedded elliptical delamination shown in Fig. 3. The permissible loading in [6] is axial load and bending moment in one direction, see Fig. 3. Reference 7 admits bi-axial loads, but no moments. Reference 6 also allows variable boundary conditions for the local buckle ranging from fully fixed to simple supports which is controlled in the computer program by a fixity factor coefficient, γ , ranging from 0 to 1. This factor can be used as a correlation factor between analysis and test. Figure 4 shows a comparison of test data and analysis results using [6] for a compression loaded 24 ply specimen with three different delamination configurations. Specimen DSC2 had a 50.8 mm (2 in.) diameter delamination embedded four plies deep from one surface; specimen DSM1 had an additional identical delamination embedded four plies deep from the opposite surface; specimen DSM2 was identical to DSM1 with a third 50.8 mm (2 in.) diameter delamination embedded at the specimen midplane. In the analysis the near surface delamination controls the failure and hence the prediction is the same for all three specimen types. The prediction is within 3% for DSC2 and DSM1 specimens as compared to test data using $\gamma = 0.33$. For specimen DSM2 better correlation was obtained by increasing the fixity coefficient to $\gamma = 0.7$ (closer to simple supports) to more realistically reflect the degraded stiffness of the inner portion of the laminate.

Fig. 3: Laminate with an elliptical delamination

Fig. 4: Comparison of observed and predicted failure strain of a 24-ply laminate with multiple delaminations

Reference 7 also employs an empirical factor, a knockdown of the buckled sublaminates' bending stiffness [D] matrix, β , which is being used to expand the delamination buckling program to model impact damage. This adjustment is guided by the observation that after an impact event many delaminations exist across the thickness. By interrogating every interface of the laminate, selecting the most critical one, and selecting β , a prediction of compression strength after an impact can be made by the software of [7]. Figures 5 and 6 from [7] show the degree of correlation for brittle and toughened resin materials that can be obtained. The predictions, made with $\beta = 0.5$, are good, particularly for the stiffer laminate. It should be noted that these predictions were made for fairly thick laminates; for thinner laminates this method may be unconservative. It should be noted that thinner laminates may have penetration damage with attendant fiber breakage as a result of impact damage and hence the assumption that delaminations control residual strength may not be applicable. The use of the delamination buckling formulation to model impact damage may be the only practical application of this formulation as a single delamination in a laminate, unless it is large, is not critical in compression loaded structure when compared to strength reductions due to notches.

Fig. 5: Compression strength of impacted Gr/Ep laminates

The analytical delamination buckling methods developed in [6,7] were extended to a laminate with a central fastener. For this case the delamination is constrained in the center but grows outwards as a ring. These analytical models are useful for determining residual strength of laminates damaged as a result of improper assembly. An engineering methodology that can address the delamination growth problem for all the delamination locations shown in Fig. 2 is being developed by Davidson under partial FAA funding. This prediction methodology [8] uses a crack tip element (CTE) analysis based on classical plate theory [9]. The CTE provides a closed form expressions for mode mix and energy release rate (ERR) in terms of force and moment resultants in the vicinity of delamination tip which are usually available from FEA of the structural component. As this procedure is computationally efficient it can be used at a large number of interfaces where

Fig. 6: Compression strength of toughened impacted Gr/Ep laminates

delamination growth is likely. Once ERR is calculated it is compared to material toughness at the appropriate mode mix ratio to determine delamination growth initiation. The material toughness in terms of ratios of G_I and G_{II} is determined experimentally using tests described in the next section. In addition, the CTE approach allows non-classical definitions of the individual ERR components. This is useful for many laminated composites when the classical linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) are inapplicable. For those cases where the near-tip damage zone is small and the classical definitions of ERR apply, solutions by the CTE approach have been compared to FEA showing excellent correlation and computing efficiency [8,9]. For non-classical LEFM, a series of experiments are required to predict delamination growth. One set, to determine the “appropriate definition” of the ERR components and mode ratio and the second set to determine the toughness vs. mode mix relation for the material of interest. These experiments are described in the next section.

DETERMINATION OF CRITICAL STRAIN ENERGY RELEASE RATES

The success of fracture mechanics analysis to predict delamination initiation and growth strongly depends on having reliable test methods to determine critical strain energy release rates. These are needed for all three fracture modes and their interactions. ASTM has been standardizing these test methods, but the progress has been very slow. For mode I there is a published standard (D5228-94) for static determination of G_{Ic} using a double cantilever beam (DCB) test, but it is unavailable under fatigue loading. For other fracture modes, including mixed modes, status of ASTM standards is at varying stages of completion. Work to date has shown that for mode II, G_{IIc} as determined by end notch flexure (ENF) test is characterized by large scatter (20%). At this time it is not clear whether it is an indication of the scatter in this material property or a consequence of the test method.

Standard tests determine G_c 's by growth of delaminations in symmetrical specimens between plies in the same direction, usually 0 plies. One such plot obtained from [8] is shown in Fig. 7. The symbols show the mean of the data (a minimum of 5 test points) while the bars show

the variability by ending the bars at ± 1 normal standard deviations. The data was generated using DCB, ENF, Mixed-Mode Bending (MMB) and Single Leg Bending (SLB) specimens [8]. Mode decomposition for mixed-mode tests were by FEA for SLB, and by closed form approach for MMB [10], and also by CTE and Williams' [11] method for all tests. For these symmetric specimens containing midplane delaminations the same values of mode mix (G_{II}/G) were obtained by all of the different mode decomposition techniques resulting in consistent G_c 's. That is for a symmetric laminate with a midplane delamination any reasonable definition of mode mix will collapse to the singular field based result.

Fig. 7: G_c vs G_{II}/G for Gr/Ep midplane delaminations

Unfortunately, in realistic aircraft structures critical areas for growth may be between dissimilar orientation plies and at unsymmetrical locations. In these instances, the prediction of mode mix using the classical approach may be significantly in error, either due to large near-tip damage zones or bridging. Davidson [8] has been investigating what value of G_c should be used in these cases. Figure 8 shows a plot of data obtained from [8] in which G_c is plotted versus mode ratio for specimens with unsymmetrically placed delaminations. The location of the delamination is shown as a slash in the legend. For example, 25/5 indicates that the starter delamination was placed 25 plies deep in a 30 ply laminate. If LFM methods are used to reduce the data, represented in Fig. 8 by upright triangles and squares, poor correlation is obtained when compared to symmetrical specimen data of Fig. 7 and reproduced in Fig. 8 as the solid and dashed lines connecting means. One would expect G_c to be a material property independent of location in a unidirectional laminate. In order to obtain better correlation, the mix mode coefficient, Ω , from the CTE, was used as a fitting parameter instead of the singular field based Ω , available as a function of thickness in [9]. This resulted in inverted triangle data points in Fig. 8, see [8] for definition of Ω . Three points to be made here are: (1) that symmetrical ASTM specimens were not sufficient to determine critical G_c at G_{II}/G ratios greater than 0.5 for this particular material, (2) additional tests to the symmetrical ASTM specimens are needed to assess if the classical definitions of ERR and mode mix solutions are valid, and (3) CTE analysis can provide a framework, until the time when the interlaminar physical behavior is understood, to make empirical adjustments to reflect reality

of delamination locations and/or to account for large damage zones. Although the CTE method has been shown to work well for unidirectional laminates its application to general lay-ups and interfaces has yet to be demonstrated. This work is presently in progress.

Fig. 8: G_c vs G_{II}/G_I for Gr/Ep midplane and offset delaminations

ANALYTICAL METHODS USAGE

There are very few examples of analytical methods usage in the industry. At this time these methods have not found their way into the mainstream of the design or certification. The methodology has been used to predict or understand element or component test results, primarily disbond failure of the skin/stringer interface. The analyses of [12,13,14] used FEA models to compute strain-energy release rates to determine delamination growth for these disbond problems.

One example where fracture mechanics approach was used was the evaluation of military aircraft control surface components that were damaged during manufacture. The results of the analysis provided the means of deciding whether the discrepant part could meet the durability requirements or should be repaired. The structure that was analyzed consisted of a Syncore sandwich where one side of the facesheet plies was inadvertently severed during the Syncore trimming operation. The resulting sandwich, idealized in Fig. 9, created a situation where under load the initial slit would progress by means of matrix cracks until it reached a stiff layer at which point a delamination would initiate. The question of durability then became a question whether these delaminations grow to a size that can be found by normal ultrasonic inspection. As ultrasonic inspection over the life of these parts was not planned, the analysis assumed an inspection threshold size as the in-situ delamination and a no-growth criterion was postulated under a simulated two lifetimes spectrum fatigue or that G_{th} would not be exceeded.

Because of the relatively complex construction and hybrid materials in the sandwich panels (Fig. 9), standard fracture mechanics tests such as DCB were not used to determine G_{th} but rather were back-calculated from test specimens that were more representative of the actual panel construction. This meant that the tests contained mixtures of modes I,II and III crack-opening displacements.

Fig. 9: Idealization of axial specimen used for strain-energy-release-rate analysis

The strain-energy-release-rate calculations were made for data reduction of test specimens, as shown in Fig. 9 for tensile loading (These were also done for compression and shear.), and actual component panels using [15]. Reference 15 treats the composite structure as an assemblage of sublaminates. Each sublaminate is treated as a higher-order plate, with shear flexibility and through the thickness stretching. When the plates are stacked the interlaminar stresses at the interfaces can be accurately evaluated. The resulting equations are solved exactly in closed form. Plates can be connected end-to-end so that complex cross-sections can be represented. However, the cross-section must be constant. A stiffness-derivative method was used to determine the total G . Alternatively, virtual crack closure method [16] was used to find the total G and its mode components. The calculated G 's for the panels were compared to the test G_{th} 's to determine margins of safety.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Analytical methods to predict damage initiation and growth have been reviewed as to their readiness to be useful in the certification process. The review has ascertained that there are available methods that can obviate the computational complexity of FEA and can replace or at least reduce testing, particularly at the element and subcomponent level. All the methods reviewed require fine tuning for specific applications using built-in correlation factors. These factors have to be obtained by test, similarly to what is done in the analysis of notched laminates. This is not a criticism, as one would not expect a purely analytical method to be able to model such complex problems. However, because of the experience required to apply these semi-empirical methods, they are usually non-transferable between companies. This leads to the main barrier why these methods have not seen widespread use and that is a lack of independent verification test data.

Determination of material G. at various mode mixes requires further research as to their applicability to a general problem. Recourse can be taken by testing coupons simulating the actual situations instead of using ASTM, or other widely used, tests on unidirectional specimens, as was illustrated by the industry usage example.

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